

HEREDITARY

HetERogeneous sEMantic Data integratlon for the guT-bRain interplaY

Deliverable 2.22

UCD clinical studies documentation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines the research, compliance, and operational framework adopted by the University of Colorado, Denver (UCD), for its role in the HEREDITARY project. The study is focused on identifying novel biomarkers for neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's Disease (PD), Alzheimer's Disease (AD), and Multiple Sclerosis (MS). Specifically, UCD aims to analyze relationships between ophthalmic imaging data (namely, Optical Coherence Tomography) and clinical metrics indicative of disease status (e.g., cognitive function scores).

The study's methodology incorporates Federated Learning (FL), a decentralized AI training approach that facilitates multi-institutional collaboration without compromising patient privacy. By using FL, institutions can collaboratively train advanced AI models without sharing raw patient data. Retrospective data spanning over a decade (01/2012 to present) is curated from UCHHealth Sue Anschutz-Rodgers Eye Center's CORIS database, ensuring that ample data is available for analysis. UCD emphasizes the importance of privacy compliance. Robust security measures such as pseudonymization, restricted access, and encrypted data storage support confidentiality throughout the study.

Here, we outline the details of the study's objectives, methodology, compliance measures, risk mitigation strategies, and anticipated outcomes in alignment with HEREDITARY's mission to advance early detection and treatment precision for neurodegenerative diseases while ensuring ethical standards in data management.

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Original version
AD	Alzheimer's Disease
AI	Artificial Intelligence
COMIRB	Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board
CORIS	Clinical Ophthalmology Retrospective Imaging System
EHR	Electronic Health Record
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act Sclerosis
IRB	Institutional Review Board
MMSE	Mini-Mental Status Exam
MOCA	Montreal Cognitive Assessment
MS	Multiple Sclerosis
OCT	Optical Coherence Tomography
PD	Parkinson's Disease
PHI	Protected Health Information
SLCE	Secure Local Compute Environment
UCD	University of Colorado Denver

1 Introduction

This deliverable outlines the framework, objectives, and compliance measures for the University of Colorado Denver's (UCD) contribution to the HEREDITARY project. Specifically, UCD is the lead of Use Case 3 "Signs of Parkinson's disease in multimodal data". Use Case 3 aims to identify biomarkers for Parkinson's disease (PD) and other neurodegenerative diseases using multimodal sources of clinical data: ophthalmic images, clinical notes, Electronic Health Record (EHR) values.

UCD's specific goals include the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) models to analyze retinal images and correlate imaging biomarkers with clinical metrics such as cognitive assessment scores (e.g., MMSE, MOCA).

In order to achieve this goal, Use Case 3 adopts a multi-step approach from lower to higher data complexity: from investigating single modality of data (i.e., ophthalmic images) from a single institution (i.e., UCD) to investigating multiple modalities (e.g., images and text and EHR data) from the same institution, to expanding the multimodal analysis to multiple institutions (e.g., UCD and UNIPD).

Regarding collecting and analyzing data from our institution, as an American institution, UCD is bound by United States laws in terms of privacy and data collection and processing. Specifically, the Health and Human Services regulation 45 CFR 46 protects human subjects in research (with subpart A, also known as the "Common Rule", providing a set of protections for research subjects). The Common Rule requires research involving human subjects to be reviewed by an Institutional Review Board (IRB): a committee of research and regulation experts at an institution that reviews research protocols to ensure the study is ethical and the participants' rights and safety are protected.

In addition, access and storage of Protected Health Information (PHI) for research purposes are also regulated by the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act of 1996 to ensure patient identifiers (i.e., pieces of information that would allow the identification of a research subject if disclosed – e.g., name, driver's license number, date of birth) are collected only if strictly necessary for the study and stored safely to minimize risks to patients.

The main data we collected at UCD for this project is sourced retrospectively from the Clinical Ophthalmology Retrospective Imaging System (CORIS) database (IRB protocol #23-0284), encompassing patients seen at the UCHealth Sue Anschutz-Rodgers Eye Center from January 2012 to present. With UCD's emphasis on maintaining data security and ethical compliance, all research activities adhere to IRB Protocols #25-2342 and #25-2326.

Additionally, UCD is in the process of prospectively collecting ophthalmic images for patients routinely seen at non-ophthalmic clinics with the goal to collect retinal scans for patients not affected by ophthalmic conditions. This data collection and analysis process has been approved by the IRB (protocol #24-2014).

Regarding analyzing data from multiple institutions, no direct data sharing can be carried out; instead, Use Case 3 will use Federated Learning (FL) to collaboratively train AI models while maintaining patient confidentiality in compliance with local laws and regulations at each institution (e.g., UCD, UNIPD). With FL, no patient data is directly

shared, but a model's parameters are shared between each institution and a central server (usually hosted at one of the participating institutions). A model's parameters represent aggregate knowledge on the data used to compute them; an active research question is thus whether it is possible to reconstruct the input data from a model's parameters. No definite answer has been accepted by the research community, especially when considering real-world experimental conditions (e.g., large batch sizes (Hatamizadeh et al. 2023)). In order to ensure that no PHI can be reconstructed, experiments in Use Case 3 will train models without any PHI (as well as additional, more technical approaches that would mask the real values of the parameters – e.g., differential privacy (Ziller et al., 2024)).

2 Data to be included in the study

The HEREDITARY project primarily utilizes UCD's retrospective observational data extracted from clinical records at the University of Colorado Hospital and Sue Anschutz Rodgers Eye Center, collected under the CORIS project, protocol #23-0284. In addition, UCD is currently prospectively recruiting patients seen at general ophthalmology clinics and at non-ophthalmological clinics (i.e., cardiology, endocrinology, general internal medicine, and neurology) at UCHealth, as well as at the CU Anschutz's Colorado Clinical and Translational Sciences Institute (CCTSI) and Barbara Davis Center, and imaging them with both OCT and Color Fundus Photography. The purpose of this prospective project (called Anschutz Accelerated Initiative, or AAI) is to collect ophthalmic images from both patients with eye conditions (i.e., seen in ophthalmology clinics), as well as from patients not affected by eye diseases in order to evaluate retinal biomarkers of systemic and neurodegenerative diseases in retinas whose appearance is not affected by other conditions that can mask or mimic signals related to systemic and neurologic health.

In HEREDITARY, data usage is governed by specific regulatory, ethical, and legal authorizations. All processing is carried out in a pseudonymized setting, maximizing privacy and security.

2.1 Summary of data provided by UCD through CORIS

The study will focus on ophthalmic imaging and clinical data retrospectively collected as part of the CORIS database.

Types of data to be included in the study:

Ophthalmic Imaging Data:

- Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) scans, providing information on retinal layer thickness and optic nerve structure.
- AI-extracted imaging features identified through model training, which are critical for uncovering subtle retinal changes linked to neurodegenerative diseases.

Clinical Data:

- Patient demographics, including age and gender.
- Cognitive assessment scores such as the Mini-Mental Status Exam (MMSE) and Montreal Cognitive Assessment (MOCA).
- Routinely assessed clinical indicators for neurodegenerative diseases referenced from EHR flowsheets, discrete fields, and free-text notes.

Cohort Selection:

- The study cohort includes patients diagnosed with neurodegenerative disorders, including Parkinson's Disease (PD), Alzheimer's Disease (AD), and Multiple Sclerosis (MS).
- An age-matched control cohort comprising individuals without a diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases will also be included.

All data has been curated in compliance with HIPAA, ensuring appropriate pseudonymization to protect patient confidentiality.

2.2 Summary of data provided by UCD through AAI

Through the AAI project, UCD is currently collecting the following sources of data:

- Ophthalmic Imaging Data:
 - Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT) scans of the macula and optic nerve
 - Color Fundus Photography
- Expert image quality assessments:
 - Each image will be reviewed by a retina and a glaucoma specialist and assessed for quality and usability for the AAI study, In addition, incidental ophthalmic findings will be recorded as well.
- Clinical Data:
 - Similarly to the CORIS database, we will have access to EHR information for the patients that consented into the AAI study

Cohort Selection:

- Inclusion criteria: patients over 18 attending one of the enrolled clinics for routine check-ups or disease management
- Exclusion criteria: any circumstances where images cannot be taken

3 Ethical conduct of the study

UCD places paramount importance on the ethical conduct of all research, particularly given the sensitive nature of patient data and the collaborative, cross-institutional frameworks enabled by the HEREDITARY project. The foundation of ethical research in this study is its strict adherence to regulatory requirements, institutional policies, and the principles of privacy, confidentiality, and minimization of harm. Key considerations include obtaining necessary approvals, appropriately managing data in compliance with privacy laws, protecting participant confidentiality, and ensuring transparency in how ethical challenges - such as incidental findings and algorithmic biases - are addressed during study execution.

The retrospective nature of this study ensures that no new data collection from patients will occur. Instead, already-collected, de-identified clinical and ophthalmic imaging data will be utilized to develop artificial intelligence (AI) models capable of identifying biomarkers for neurodegenerative diseases. However, despite the minimal risk to participants involved in secondary research reliant on existing datasets, rigorous ethical protocols remain a cornerstone of the research process. The following sections outline how ethical oversight and compliance activities have been integrated into UCD's approach to participation in the HEREDITARY project.

3.1 Ethical Approvals

In accordance with regulatory and institutional requirements, clearances for the HEREDITARY program have been sought and approved by the Colorado Multiple Institutional Review Board (COMIRB). Three IRB protocols underpin the ethical and scientific validity of UCD's contributions:

- **Protocol #23-0284:** Titled "Clinical Ophthalmology Retrospective Imaging System (CORIS)". This protocol allows UCD to periodically collect and store ophthalmic images and EHR data for patients seen at the UHealth Sue Anschutz-Rodgers Eye Center from January 2012. While the protocol includes AI-powered analysis of such data, UCD also requires project specific IRBs to ensure withholding high ethical standards with each use of the CORIS dataset.
- **Protocol #25-2326:** Titled "*Relationship between clinical metrics for neurodegenerative diseases and ophthalmic imaging biomarkers,*" this protocol specifically focuses on the exploratory task of correlating routinely collected clinical metrics, such as cognitive function scores, with ophthalmic imaging biomarkers.
- **Protocol #25-2342:** Titled "*Identification of biomarkers for neurodegenerative diseases from ophthalmic images and clinical data using Federated Learning,*" this protocol covers the primary objectives and methodological approaches associated with UCD's use of both imaging and clinical metrics to develop generalizable AI models within a Federated Learning (FL) framework.
- **Protocol #24-2014:** Titled "*AI and Oculomics for Systemic Disease Detection*", this protocol focuses on discovering retinal biomarkers for systemic and neurological diseases from patients not affected by ophthalmic diseases, in order to prevent disease features from masking any signal predictive of

systemic health.

The COMIRB formally reviewed and approved these protocols based on their feasibility, scientific validity, risk mitigation strategies, and ethical safeguards (approval certificates are attached in the annex). Regular compliance monitoring and interim reviews will ensure that the goals of the research are achieved while upholding participant protections.

Informed consent from retrospectively collected participants was waived in protocols #33-0284, #25-2326, and #25-2342 due to infeasibility of obtaining it from all the patients ever seen at the UCHealth Sue Anschutz-Rodgers Eye Center from January 2012.

Given its prospective nature, informed consent is required for protocol #24-2014. Paper consent will be provided to the subjects during their medical visit; on the online platform, the subjects can read it on the iPad and a copy will be sent to the subject's email address. In any instance, the photographer (who has been trained on ethical conduct of research) must explain what and why the subject will be consenting to. Also, the investigational subject will be informed that consenting is voluntary, and the subject can drop off at any time during the investigation. The consent will be articulated in plain language for investigational subjects or Legal Adult Representative to understand the purpose of it. Also, the consent will be informing the investigational subject that the data produced will be shared with the investigational team for research purposes.

3.2 Ethical Framework

The ethical safeguards employed by UCD not only align with regulatory compliance requirements such as HIPAA and GDPR but also draw on best practices in clinical informatics and responsible AI development. The following ethical principles guide the HEREDITARY project's execution:

1. Respect for Patient Confidentiality:

Protecting patient confidentiality is of utmost importance, especially given the potential sensitivity of imaging and clinical data. Only authorized personnel, who have undergone comprehensive training in handling Protected Health Information (PHI), have access to CORIS data. These individuals are trained under HIPAA guidelines and are required to follow strict protocols concerning data minimization and pseudonymization.

To preserve confidentiality, all datasets are de-identified prior to analysis. Identifiable elements, such as names, medical record numbers, or other patient attributes that carry the risk of re-identification, are removed or replaced with randomly generated codes (pseudonymization). By utilizing Secure Local Compute Environment (SLCE) and additional secure platforms such as the HIPAA-compliant Google Cloud Platform and Eureka, multiple security layers are implemented to ensure confidential data handling at all stages of research.

2. Minimization of Risk:

This study does not involve direct intervention or interaction with patients, thus minimizing the risks typically associated with research participation. The main risk is a breach of data confidentiality, which the study mitigates using advanced security mechanisms and restricted data access. These measures include password-protected systems, data encryption, role-based access controls, and periodic audits of data usage logs to ensure compliance.

The Federated Learning methodology fundamentally reduces risk to participants by ensuring that no raw patient data leaves the secure environments overseen by UCD's research team. Instead, only aggregated model parameters derived through analysis are transferred between institutional partners and centralized servers. Such parameters are furthermore perturbed so that the aggregated information they contain is further masked, reducing the risk of using them to reveal identifiable patient information.

We also ensured that all the images used for Federated Learning do not have patient information superimposed to the image itself by only considering images from devices that do not print such information on the images. Should some of the devices that do print such information on the images be included in the study, we will adopt a set of computer vision techniques developed by our lab to remove such information.

3. Addressing Algorithmic Bias:

Since AI algorithms operate on historical data, there may be a risk of embedded biases in the datasets or the models that are trained. For example, age has previously been identified as a confounding factor in using ophthalmic imaging to identify biomarkers of neurodegenerative diseases. During prior research efforts, AI models mistakenly learned to use a patient's age at the time of imaging as a proxy for disease status, resulting in biased predictions. To address these types of biases in HEREDITARY, UCD researchers will ensure proper cohort selection by using age-matched controls. Continuous assessments of model predictions will include fairness testing to identify and mitigate potential biases during model development. Findings related to possible biases will be communicated to IRB oversight bodies and clinical leadership as part of the study's commitment to transparent reporting.

4. Transparency and Communication of Findings:

All ethical concerns, such as incidental findings or previously unrecognized biases, are promptly documented and addressed. For example, if model outputs inadvertently indicate new patterns or associations not directly linked to core research questions, such information may be flagged for review by subject-matter experts or clinical panels, fostering transparency and open dialogue between researchers and oversight committees.

3.3 Ethical Approval Documentation

All necessary ethical approval documentation, including finalized IRB protocols and any amendments submitted to accommodate iterative research objectives can be provided upon request. COMIRB approval letters are attached in the annex.

4 Data Management

UCD's approach to data management has been specifically designed to align with the Federated Learning (FL) framework used in the project, which avoids direct data sharing or transfer between institutions. This ensures that participant confidentiality and data security remain paramount throughout the research process. The following sections outline the protocols and methodologies associated with data minimization, data security, pseudonymization, and Federated Learning workflows.

4.1 Data Minimization and Pseudonymization

One of the central pillars of UCD's data management approach is data minimization. This refers to the practice of collecting, processing, and storing only the minimal amount of data necessary to achieve the research objectives. This involves rigorous oversight during the data curation phase to ensure that researchers do not gain access to more information than is essential for the development of AI models or analysis of neurodegenerative biomarkers.

Before any data is accessed by research personnel, raw clinical and imaging datasets are subjected to pseudonymization. Pseudonymization ensures that all personally identifiable information (PII) from the dataset is replaced with randomly generated alphanumeric codes. Identifiable variables such as patient names, addresses, dates of service, and medical record numbers are either removed or replaced under stringent pseudonymization protocols. A master list linking pseudonymized codes to identifiers is created and securely stored in a separate access-restricted environment, ensuring that re-identification is limited to a few trusted data managers (if deemed necessary for compliance audits or incidental findings).

4.2 Secure Storage and Access Management

All data in CORIS is managed and stored in the Secure Local Compute Environment (SLCE) provided by the Information Services team at the CU Anschutz School of Medicine. SLCE is built to support research involving sensitive and protected health information (PHI), adhering to encryption, access control, and monitoring standards as outlined below:

- **Access Controls:** Each authorized user is assigned an individual login credential, with permissions granted only to study personnel approved under COMIRB protocols. Access to SLCE is granted on a role-based basis; users only have access to the specific dataset segments necessary for their role within the project.
- **Encryption and Secure Network:** The SLCE environment requires users to access data exclusively via the CU Anschutz campus network or through a Virtual Private Network (VPN). All stored data is encrypted using advanced encryption standards (AES).
- **System Monitoring and Audits:** Security software actively monitors the SLCE environment for suspicious activity. All access and data usage logs are

periodically audited to ensure compliance and review any anomalous activity.

In addition to SLCE, HIPAA-compliant cloud platforms such as the Google Cloud Platform and Eureka are utilized for redundancy and scalability purposes. Both platforms mirror the security protocols employed within SLCE, ensuring equivalent standards for data confidentiality and restricted access.

4.3 Federated Learning and Model Parameter Management

A defining characteristic of the HEREDITARY project is its implementation of Federated Learning (FL), which eliminates the need for direct data sharing between UCD and its European HEREDITARY collaborators. FL allows institutions to collaboratively train AI models on decentralized data located on-site at individual institutions. The data remains within UCD's servers, and only the trained model's parameters (i.e., weights representing aggregated insights) are shared with a designated central server.

Key safeguards implemented as part of the FL process include:

- **Privacy-Preserving Aggregation:** To protect prevent reverse-engineering of input data from models' parameters, techniques such as differential privacy will be employed. Differential privacy works by adding noise to the parameters exchanged during FL updates, thus reducing the likelihood of reconstructing input data from the aggregate parameters.
- **Whitelisted Network Protocols:** Only specific, pre-approved IP addresses of collaborating HEREDITARY nodes will be allowed to connect to UCD's server. Inbound and outbound network access is carefully monitored.

These measures ensure that no identifiable patient-level information or raw data ever leaves UCD, protecting participant confidentiality while enabling collaborative research.

4.4 Data Transfers to Third Parties and International Transfers

No raw patient data from UCD will be transferred to third parties or external collaborators as part of this study. The project operates entirely under the principles of data localization, where sensitive data remains within UCD's domain during its analytic lifecycle. UCD's Study Team recognizes that even non-identifiable data and metadata can create risks during cross-border collaborations. As a result, direct data-sharing is prohibited, and the Federated Learning model-sharing methodology eliminates the need for international data transfers.

Model parameters transferred between UCD and the HEREDITARY central server comply with both U.S. and European privacy regulations. International transfers of model parameters occur over encrypted networks, with security protocols in place to ensure data integrity and guard against interception by malicious third parties.

4.5 Risk Mitigation Measures for Data Confidentiality

While the HEREDITARY project at UCD operates under a secondary-use research framework with no direct patient interaction, potential risks to data confidentiality remain a priority. To mitigate these risks, UCD employs several levels of safeguards:

1. **Access Revocation:** User permissions are immediately revoked upon personnel termination from the project or institution. Access is regularly evaluated to ensure only active, authorized personnel can access project data.
2. **Periodic Data Validation:** Dataset integrity and pseudonymization are reviewed routinely to verify that identifiers remain sufficiently anonymized according to the latest regulatory standards.
3. **Incident Monitoring System:** In the event of an attempted data breach or access anomaly, automated alerts are triggered, prompting immediate review and further action from IT security specialists.

5 Incidental Findings Policy

While the HEREDITARY study is designed as a secondary analysis of existing data and does not involve direct patient interaction, there remains the potential for incidental findings to emerge during the examination of retinal health data or AI model outputs. These findings could include indicators of retinal anomalies that are not directly related to the study's primary aim of identifying biomarkers for neurodegenerative diseases, or previously unrecognized biases within the data or machine-learning pipelines. Identifying and addressing such findings is critical to ensuring ethical research practices and maintaining the integrity of the study's outcomes.

In the case of retinal health observations, the AI algorithms may detect unexpected patterns or anomalies within the ophthalmic imaging data that suggest undiagnosed or unreported ocular conditions, such as indications of glaucoma, diabetic retinopathy, or macular degeneration. Though these findings are beyond the scope of the project's objectives, they may hold clinical importance for patient health. To manage these situations, UCD has established a process to communicate such findings with the clinical leadership at UCD. By leveraging existing UCD channels, these incidental observations can be investigated further under clinical protocols, ensuring patient care considerations are addressed responsibly and within the appropriate medical context.

Similarly, incidental identification of algorithmic biases presents another area of concern. AI models trained on historical datasets may sometimes produce outputs reflective of imbalances or systemic biases inherent in the training data, such as disparities in age distribution, gender representation, or disease status within the cohorts. If such biases are discovered, they will be meticulously documented and evaluated by the research team. Adjustments will then be made to the model design or training pipeline to mitigate these issues and improve the accuracy and fairness of AI predictions. Findings related to biases will be transparently shared with institutional reviewers to ensure accountability and adherence to ethical guidelines.

The overarching aim in managing incidental findings is to simultaneously protect patient welfare and improve the reliability of AI models developed under the HEREDITARY study. Whether the findings are purely clinical or related to data integrity, UCD strives to balance scientific discovery with ethical research standards. Transparent communication with clinical stakeholders and institutional review boards allows the study team to address findings responsibly, ensuring that the research remains grounded in patient-centered and ethically sound practice.

6 Conclusion

This deliverable outlines UCD's methodological, ethical, and operational commitments for its participation in the HEREDITARY project. By leveraging ophthalmic and clinical data and Federated Learning, UCD aims to identify novel neurodegenerative disease biomarkers while preserving patient data privacy. The study capitalizes on the richness of the CORIS database, combining cutting-edge AI methodologies with robust data governance practices.

The research's anticipated contributions include more accurate, non-invasive diagnostic tools, increased understanding of retinal biomarkers, and scalable AI models applicable across diverse populations. UCD remains committed to advancing the HEREDITARY project's mission to improve disease detection, monitoring, and outcomes for patients with neurodegenerative diseases.

References

The bibliographic entries are arranged in lexicographical order based on the key, following the APA style. This enables us to place the entries and citations in the table and text in any sequence, allowing for later sorting while ensuring consistency.

Key	Reference
Hatamizadeh et al. 2023	Hatamizadeh, A., Yin, H., Molchanov, P., Myronenko, A., Li, W., Dogra, P., ... & Roth, H. R. (2023). Do gradient inversion attacks make federated learning unsafe?. <i>IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging</i> , 42(7), 2044-2056. https://doi.org/10.1109/TMI.2023.3239391
Ziller et al. 2024	Ziller, A., Mueller, T. T., Stieger, S., Feiner, L. F., Brandt, J., Braren, R., ... & Kaissis, G. (2024). Reconciling privacy and accuracy in AI for medical imaging. <i>Nature Machine Intelligence</i> , 6(7), 764-774. https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-024-00858-y

Annex

Annex	Name
1	Certificate of Exemption